

Panicle development stage at time of spraying	Pollen fertility (%)					Spikelet fertility (%) on bagged panicle					Seed set on open-pollinated panicle				
	30	40	50	60	Check	30	40	50	60	Check	30	40	50	60	V20A
	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm		ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm		ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	(check)
Branch differentiation	7.5	7.8	6.0	7.1	7.7	1.3	1.3	1.4	1.4	1.39					
Spikelet differentiation	3.5	3.1	3.1	3.5	7.1	1.1	1.2	1.2	1.1	1.3					
Reduction division of pollen mother cell	1.1	1.1	0	0	7.4	0.5	0.5	0	0	1.4			9.8	9.8	11.4
Pollen wall (exine) formation	0	0	0	0	7.3	0	0	0	0	1.4	10.3	10.1	10.2	10.0	11.0

- At branch differentiation stage, there was no difference in pollen fertility and self-fertilization between materials sprayed with the male gametocide and check. The male gametocide had no effect on the young panicle.
- At the spikelet differentiation stage, there was obvious difference, but effectiveness was low.

- At the reduction division stage of the pollen mother cell, effectiveness of 30 and 40 ppm spray was best.
 - At the pollen exine stage, all spray levels were effective, with no fertile pollen in the anther and no self-fertilization.
- We concluded the effect of low temperature can be controlled and complete

pollen sterility of CIS28-15 maintained by spraying with the male gametocide 5 d before heading, at the pollen exine stage. A second treatment may be necessary to sterilize all tillers at the appropriate development stage.

The treatment does not affect the outcrossing rate of CIS28-15. ■

Yield potential

Genetic nature of high-density rice grain

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In 1988 dry season, we studied the genetic nature of HD grain production using the parents, F₁, F₂, and two backcrosses of Rewa 353-5/IR56, IR56/Rewa 353, and Rewa 353-4/IR28211-43-1-1-2. Single seeds of the six generations were sown separately in 4-liter pots containing 3 kg of Maahas clay soil (Andaqueptic Haplaquolls) mixed with 4 g ammonium

sulfate, 2 g single superphosphate, and 2 g muriate of potash. The number of HD grains produced on primary branches (Pb) and secondary branches (Sb) of the panicles was determined by salt solution.

Mean data from 15 plants of parents and F₁, 50 plants of backcrosses, and 100 plants of F₂ were used for analysis. The HD grain index (HDI) was calculated as the number of HD grains divided by the number of spikelets per plant.

The parents differed significantly in number of HD grains and HDI (Table 1). Rewa 353-5 had the most HD grains (1,088) but IR28211-43-1-1-2 had the highest HDI (53.2%). Although heterobeltiosis for number of HD grains was 113% for F₁ of IR56/Rewa 353 and 50%

for Rewa 353-4/IR28211-43-1-1-2, the HDI of Rewa 353-4/IR28211-43-1-1-2 was very close to that of the higher parent because of the higher number of spikelets. The HDI of Rewa 353-5/IR56 was much lower than the mid-parent value.

In all crosses, mean HD grain was lower in the F₂ than in the F₁ and the better parent. Backcrosses with the better parent produced more HD grains than backcrosses with the lower parent. The F₂ plants produced more than the better parent.

These results indicate scope for selecting of parents and the possibility of getting heterotic lines from such crosses.

Estimates of gene effects (Table 2) indicate highly significant additive and

Table 1. Mean HD grains in 6 generations of Rewa 353-5/IR56 (1), IR56/Rewa 353 (2), and Rewa 353-4/IR28211-43-1-1-2 (3). IRRI, 1988.

Generation	HD grain/plant (no.)									High density grain index		
	Primary branch			Secondary branch			Total HD grain (no.)					
	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
P ₁	475p5.4	253p5.3	244p4.7	613p7.7	317p 7.1	399p9.4	1088	570	643	47.6	33.3	33.8
P ₂	253p5.3	273p8.2	530p5.3	317p7.1	419p10.8	398p6.1	570	692	928	33.3	25.9	53.2
F ₁	228p4.4	704p5.7	731p5.0	357p6.8	771p 8.7	719p3.8	585	1475	1450	23.1	53.6	54.7
F ₂	182p4.1	248p4.6	411p7.3	204p5.7	359p 7.2	440p7.5	386	607	851	18.3	27.4	38.9
BC ₁	274p4.5	203p8.8	173p4.6	376p9.7	220p12.8	215p7.2	650	423	388	27.9	17.5	18.8
BC ₂	9p0.6	389p5.9	695p9.2	10p0.8	595p 8.6	561p8.9	19	984	1256	1.0	41.1	62.7

dominance effects for Rewa 353-S/IR56 and IR56/Rewa 353. In Rewa 353-4/IR2811-43-1-1-2, only the additive effects were significant for both Pb and Sb. Among the epistatic effects, additive/dominance was significant for all crosses. In Rewa 353-5/IR56, dominance/dominance was also significant for Pb and Sb. Duplicate epistasis indicated by the negative value of 'h' and positive value of 'l' in Rewa 353-5/IR56 may hinder selection.

Heritability estimates for both Pb and Sb were high in Rewa 353-5/IR56 and Rewa 353-4/IR2811-43-1-1-2 and low in IR56/Rewa 353. Estimates of the number of effective factors were very low for Rewa 353-5/IR56, but two and above for IR56/Rewa 353 and Rewa 353-4/IR2811-43-1-1-2.

With the significant additive effects and high heritability in Rewa 353-5/IR56 and Rewa 353-4/IR2811-43-1-1-2, mass

selection in early generations to improve heterogeneous populations by modifying the frequencies of desirable genes, followed by single plant selection, may be advantageous in increasing the number of HD grains. Because of high variation due to dominance and epistatic effects in IR56/Rewa 353, selection in later generations would be better, to diminish dominance effects. ■

Table 2. Estimates of gene effects for number of HD grains in Rewa 353-5/IR56 (1), IR56/Rewa 353 (2), and Rewa 353-4/IR2811-43-1-1-2 (3). IRR1, 1989.

Parameter	Primary branch			Secondary branch		
	1	2	3	1	2	3
Mean	182* π 18.7	248**π 20.4	411** π 73.2	204** π 25.9	359**π 32.0	440** π 75.1
Additive	265**π 20.2	186**π 42.4	- 522** π 103.2	366* π 43.5	- 375**π 61.7	- 346** π 114.6
Dominance	- 298**π 51.3	633**π 122.2	436 π 369.9	- 152 π 98.2	597**π 184.0	113 π 383.4
Additive/additive	- 162 π 85.0	- 8 π 117.8	92 π 358.3	- 44 π 135.4	194 π 177.9	- 208 π 377.7
Additive/dominance	391**π 25.5	- 176**π 43.0	- 379** π 110.6	524** π 48.4	- 324**π 67.2	- 346** π 126.6
Dominance/dominance	780**π 121.3	558**π 119.3	408 π 521.9	916** π 215.8	454 π 293.6	891 π 563.6
Heritability	70.7	15.6	85.2	58.8	14.6	83.5
Effective factors	0.5	5.5	13.6	0.7	1.5	6.1

** = significant at the 1% level.

Genotypic differences in rice yield potential and N, P, and K in leaves

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We studied the yield potential and leaf N, P, and K at peak growth (55 d) in 27 rice genotypes. Soil was alluvial, sandy loam, and alkaline, with pH 7.8, 0.061% N, 0.05% P, 0.45% K, 4.5 ppm available P, and 0.14% total soluble solids. Standard 120 kg N and 60 kg P/ha were broadcast and incorporated before planting. There were 16 hills/m². The plots were laid out in a randomized design with four replications. Normal agronomic practices were followed. The first fully emerged leaf from each genotype was collected at 55 d and its N, P, and K content measured.

Leaves were dried and ground in a wiley mill. A 1-g sample was digested using H₂SO₄ and H₂O₂. P was determined colorimetrically by the vanadomolybdo-yellow color method; N, by micro-kjeldahl method; and K, by flame photometer. Straw and grain yields were measured at harvest (115 d).

Yield potential of rice genotypes and N, P, and K content in plant leaf.

Rice genotype	Straw yield (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Leaf nutrient content (% dry wt)		
			N	P	K
IR6 (control)	8.1	5.5	1.54	0.31	1.86
Mutant IR6-18	6.6	5.0	1.40	0.33	1.96
Mutant IR6-93	6.7	4.7	1.35	0.29	1.81
Mutant IR6-104	7.2	3.8	0.77	0.28	1.79
Mutant IR6-113	7.0	4.6	0.77	0.30	1.69
IR8 (parent)	8.2	6.1	2.10	0.29	1.75
Mutant IR8-5	6.8	5.2	1.82	0.28	1.80
Bas 370 (parent)	12.0	3.4	1.82	0.30	1.89
Mutant 370-1	6.7	1.9	1.60	0.25	1.63
Mutant 370-5	11.0	2.3	1.49	0.27	1.67
Mutant 370-24	7.1	2.9	1.59	0.28	1.48
Mutant 370-28	6.7	2.8	1.69	0.29	1.53
Jajai 77 (parent)	13.5	3.6	2.03	0.31	1.58
Jajai 77-1	12.8	2.9	1.26	0.24	1.73
Mutant 77-2	6.5	1.7	1.61	0.31	1.33
Mutant LG-1	6.6	1.9	1.73	0.30	1.43
Mutant Jajai 30	8.4	2.1	1.69	0.28	1.53
Sada Gulab (parent)	12.8	2.7	1.82	0.30	1.63
Mutant SG-EF/SD-78	10.7	2.0	1.12	0.27	1.77
Mutant SG-EF/SD-55	9.2	2.1	1.54	0.24	1.61
Sonahri SG (parent)	17.9	5.2	1.68	0.24	1.66
Mutant SS-EF/SD-6	10.6	3.2	1.26	0.28	1.60
Mutant SS-EF/SD-8	10.5	2.6	1.26	0.23	1.53
Pokkali (parent)	7.0	3.8	1.87	0.29	1.63
Mutant pokkali	5.7	3.2	1.75	0.26	1.73
Lateefy (Dokri)	5.5	3.1	1.68	0.27	1.68
DR82 (parent)	6.7	3.7	1.70	0.28	1.69
LSD (0.05)	4.2	2.0	0.40	ns	ns
(0.01)	5.5	2.7	0.50	ns	ns